

THE IMPORTANCE OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS IN EDUCATING A SPIRITUALLY COMPLETE AND PHYSICALLY HEALTHY GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

In the article, consideration of the rights and freedoms of a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation, as well as the main directions established in this regard, are presented. It is recognized that every pedagogue should know these rights and freedoms in the process of education and upbringing of children.

Keywords: child, law, convention, education, upbringing, law.

INTRODUCTION

Children are our wealth. It is the duty not only of parents, but also of the whole society to raise a spiritually mature generation and create favorable conditions for it to grow up physically healthy. To be diligently committed to this duty and to fulfill it, every citizen, especially the teachers and trainers who provide education and training, should know the rights of the child perfectly. Organization of the education and upbringing process taking into account the rights of the child will cause the formation of the young generation as a person, as well as their rights and freedoms, as well as their duties and responsibilities, following an example.

METHODS

First of all, if we define a child and his person, a child (children) is a person (persons) up to the age of 18 (adult). [1]

Another aspect of the state policy regarding youth conducted in our country, one of its foundations is the adoption of the law on guarantees of children's rights. It contains the main directions of the state policy on the protection of children's rights, which are as follows:

- ensuring the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the child;
- protection of the child's life and health;
- not allowing the child to be discriminated against;
- protecting the honor and dignity of the child;
- ensure equality of children's rights and opportunities;
- improving the legal basis of child rights and guarantees;

to ensure the openness and transparency of the activities of state bodies and their officials in the provision and protection of children's rights, freedoms and legal interests;

to support children's physical, intellectual, spiritual and moral development;

training of personnel performing activities in the field of protection of children's rights, improving their qualifications and retraining them;

education of children's feelings of patriotism, citizenship, tolerance and love of peace;

to acquaint the child with the historical and national traditions, spiritual values and achievements of the world culture of the people of Uzbekistan;

development of the child's personality, his scientific, technical and artistic creativity;

supporting children's initiatives;

formation of legal consciousness and legal culture in the child;

cooperation between state bodies and non-governmental non-profit organizations in order to ensure children's rights;

development of cooperation with international organizations working in the field of child rights protection;

to help children's social skills and reduce delinquency among minors. [1]

RESULTS

Indeed, guaranteeing the children's freedom during the lesson creates a foundation for their creative thinking. Because for creative thinking, first of all, you need to think, and to have an independent opinion, you need freedom. In this regard, it is necessary to be concerned about his life and health, to pay attention to the products and water they consume. In this regard, it is possible to cite many goals that are expected to be implemented. In this regard, the bodies of state power and management exercise the following powers within the framework of their duties:

formation and implementation of a unified state policy on ensuring children's rights;

setting priorities for ensuring children's rights;

development and implementation of state programs and regional programs for ensuring children's rights, freedoms and legal interests;

coordination and control of activities of state bodies, children's institutions, organizations for ensuring children's rights;

financing activities related to the implementation of the state policy on the protection of children's rights in accordance with the established procedure at the expense of the funds of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other sources not prohibited by law;

take measures to strengthen the material and technical base of state-owned children's institutions and support the development of non-state children's institutions;
monitoring the fulfillment of the international obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding the issues of ensuring children's rights and representing the interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international organizations;
implementation of information and educational activities;
solving issues of support for children in need of social protection.

State authorities and management bodies may exercise other powers in accordance with the law.

In order to ensure the protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the child, to coordinate the activities of state bodies and other bodies, organizations on the protection of the rights of the child, an authorized body on the rights of the child may be established in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation.[2]

DISCUSSION

It should be emphasized that for the development of a child's personality in a healthy and harmonious manner, he needs to grow up in the care of the family, in a situation of happiness, love and conscious understanding. It is also necessary to take into account that the child should be fully prepared for an independent life in society and brought up in the spirit of peace, dignity, patience, freedom, equality and solidarity. As stated in the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, "a child, if he is physically and mentally immature, is entitled to special protection and care, and consequently to an adequate level of legal protection before and after birth. need" should be taken into account. [3]

CONCLUSION

Every person working in the field of pedagogy must follow the rights and freedoms of the child in the process of education. Every pedagogue should feel that he is on par with a mature specialist in the future in teaching a child during the lesson. At the same time, it is important to educate them as individuals who love the Motherland and are loyal to their duties and responsibilities. [4], [5], [6]

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